

**DIFICULTADES DE TRADUCCIÓN
Y DE TRANSFERENCIA CULTURAL DEL RUMANO AL ESPAÑOL
EN LA OBRA “GRĂDINA DE STICLĂ” DE TATIANA ȚÎBULEAC /
DIFFICULTIES OF TRANSLATION
AND CULTURAL TRANSFER FROM ROMANIAN INTO SPANISH
IN THE NOVEL “GRĂDINA DE STICLĂ” BY TATIANA TIBULEAC**

Tatiana GOREA, Assistant Professor, PhD Student
("Alecu Russo" Balti State University, Republic of Moldova)

tatiana.gorea@usarb.md, <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-2214-9940>

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The research deals with the analysis of the main challenges involved in translating the novel *Gradina de sticla* by Tatiana Tibuleac, from Romanian into Spanish. One of the primary difficulties lies in the use of Moldovan dialects. Additionally, the novel is deeply shaped by the Soviet and post-Soviet context and the constant presence of bilingualism, with a mixture of languages, especially Russian and "Moldovan". Translating this novel is not only a linguistic task, but also an exercise in cultural and emotional interpretation.